

SEYCHELLES NATIONAL SEAGRASS MONITORING PROTOCOLS

A Tiered Framework for Science, Conservation, Restoration and Citizen Science

SEYCHELLES CONSERVATION
AND CLIMATE ADAPTATION
TRUST

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STANDARDISED **SEAGRASS** ASSESSMENT, MONITORING AND RESTORATION
PROTOCOLS FOR SEYCHELLES

Field Procedure

Prepared for: SeyCCAT

Prepared by: Léo Barret & Gilberte Gendron, Bee Ecological Consulting

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Seagrass Monitoring Protocol – Core

BEFORE DEPARTURE – PREPARATION

1. Review the monitoring schedule, protocols and monitored indicators
2. Confirm the sentinel site, location, and region code and metadata (Annex 2)
3. Review and pack the full equipment list
4. Localise **Permanent Marker (See Note)**¹ of Sentinel Site
5. Start GPS tracking and take a picture of GPS date and time

Equipment List

	1 × 50 m fibreglass measuring tapes (Minimum)
	1 × GPS
	Compass
	1 × standard quadrat (50 × 50 cm)
	3 × monitoring datasheets (waterproof paper or slates) based on datasheet in Annex 3.
	3 × Pencils
	1 × 30 cm ruler
	1 × Camera with fully charged batteries and sufficient memory/disk space available
	Percent cover standard sheets (calibration photo guides)
	Seagrass identification sheet or App

¹ **Permanent Marker Note:** To minimise physical disturbance to seagrass beds, permanent markers for sentinel sites should preferentially rely on existing natural features at the location (e.g., stable rock outcrops) where feasible and clearly identifiable.

Where natural features are not suitable or sufficiently stable, artificial markers may be installed using a rebar stake with a surface or subsurface buoy. In such cases, the following best practices apply:

- Select placement that avoids dense or sensitive seagrass patches and minimises trampling during installation and subsequent access.
- Use a rebar of appropriate diameter and corrosion resistance.
- Ensure the rebar is firmly driven into the substrate to a minimum depth of 50 cm to guarantee long-term stability and reduce the risk of movement or scour.
- Keep the surface footprint minimal and clearly mark the location to prevent repeated repositioning.

TRANSECT AND QUADRAT PLACEMENT (REQUIRED)

A – TRANSECT PLACEMENT

1. Place or Locate the **permanent marker (See Note)¹⁸** for the site (origin point of the transect).
2. Start GPS tracking and take a picture of GPS date and time
3. Set the compass bearing:
 - a. Use a bearing perpendicular to the shoreline, oriented from shallow to deeper water.
 - b. Read the compass accurately and record the bearing on the data sheet.
4. Lay out the 50 m transect line along the recorded compass bearing. Ensure the tape is taut and follows a straight line (Figure 2).

B - RECORD TRANSECT METADATA

At the beginning of the transect, Record:

- | | |
|---|---|
| 5. Site code | 10. GPS coordinates at the end (50 m) -
In Decimal Degrees to 5 decimal places (e.g. -4.12345, 45.12345) |
| 6. Transect number | 11. Compass bearing used. |
| 7. Observer names and organisations
(full name + surname) | 12. Take a picture of the slate |
| 8. Date | |
| 9. GPS coordinates at the start (0 m) -
In Decimal Degrees to 5 decimal places (e.g. -4.12345, 45.12345) | |

C - QUADRAT PLACEMENT AND MEASUREMENT

13. Quadrats are placed on the right side of the transect line.
14. **Place 11 quadrats at 5 m intervals:** 0 m, 5 m, 10 m, ... 50 m
15. Always start at 0 m to maintain consistent sampling.
16. At each quadrat position:
 - Take a **photograph of the quadrat** before taking any other measurements.
 - Take photo before disturbing sediment (avoid resuspension).
 - Collect data for Indicator 1, 2 and 3(Required).
 - Collect data for optional indicators

D - SECOND TRANSECT PLACEMENT

17. From the permanent marker, measure 25 m to the left.
18. Mark the starting point and lay the transect using the same compass bearing as Transect 1.
19. Repeat all procedures from Sections B to C

E-THIRD TRANSECT PLACEMENT

20. From the permanent marker, measure 25 m to the right.
21. Lay the transect along the same compass bearing.
22. Repeat all procedures from Sections B to C
- 23. Move to next Sentinel Site – Repeat from Section A**

Frequency: Bi annual during the calm season (April-May) and (October-November).

Figure 1..Example of a Sentinel Site with three permanent fixed transects (50 m in length, spaced 25 m apart) established in an *Enhalus acoroides* seagrass meadow at Baie Sainte Anne, Praslin.

INDICATOR 1. SEAGRASS COVER (REQUIRED) AND 2. MACROALGAE COVER (REQUIRED)

Unit: Percent cover (%)

Equipment: Quadrat (50 × 50 cm), percent cover photo guides (calibration sheets), clipboard, datasheet and camera.

Definition: Seagrass cover and macroalgae cover are estimated separately by visual assessment. Because they can overlap, their combined total may exceed 100%.

“Plant cover” is defined as the relative area of a species when projected vertically onto the substrate surface, irrespective of whether the species forms the uppermost canopy or occurs beneath other vegetation². Plant cover must not be confused with top cover (canopy cover), which records only the uppermost visible layer.

Because plant cover accounts for overlapping vegetation layers, the sum of cover values across species or functional groups may exceed 100%. For example, a species may have substantial plant cover while having a top cover of zero if it occurs entirely beneath another canopy.

Cover Categories:

At each quadrat, cover is estimated separately for the following categories (See Annex. Benthic Category):

- Seagrass (by species)
- Macroalgae
- Abiotic
- Other visible benthic features (See Annex 4.)

Procedure - Seagrass Cover:

1. After photographing the quadrat, visually estimate total seagrass plant cover, defined as the percentage of the quadrat area occupied by all seagrass leaves and shoots when projected onto the substrate, regardless of whether they are overlain by macroalgae or other vegetation.
2. If total seagrass cover is < 3%, count all visible seagrass shoots within the quadrat and convert to cover using the agreed approximation: 1 shoot ≈ 0.1% cover (species- and size-dependent).
3. Record total seagrass plant cover (%).
4. Identify all seagrass species present in the quadrat in accordance with Indicator 2 (Seagrass Species Composition).
5. For each seagrass species, directly estimate and record its plant cover (%), based on the total area of that species within the quadrat (see Figure 3).
6. Ensure that the sum of species-specific seagrass covers equals the total seagrass plant cover (%).

² Wilson, J. B. (2011). Cover plus: Ways of measuring plant canopies and the terms used for them. *Journal of Vegetation Science*

Procedure - MacroAlgae Cover:

1. From above the quadrat, estimate % cover of **macroalgae**.
2. Macroalgae may:
 - a. Cover bare substrate, and/or
 - b. Overlie seagrass canopies.
3. Record total macroalgae plant cover (%) using the same visual estimation method and photo guides.

Procedure – Other Cover Categories

1. Estimate and record cover (%) for other visible features following the same projection principle.
2. These categories are recorded independently and may overlap with seagrass or macroalgae cover where applicable.

Frequency: At every quadrat (11 quadrats per transect, 3 transect per Site, each monitoring event).

Methodological Notes

Cover values represent total area, not canopy dominance.

Because vegetation may overlap, total cover across all categories and species may exceed 100%.

Plant cover is particularly appropriate for assessing total vegetation presence and persistence, while canopy/top cover is more appropriate for assessing dominance and light obstruction (Wilson, 2011).

Figure 2. Seagrass Percentage Cover Calibration Sheet from Seagrass Watch.

INDICATOR 3: SEAGRASS SPECIES COMPOSITION (REQUIRED)

Unit: Percent composition (%) of each species within total seagrass cover

Linked indicator: Indicator 1 – Plant Cover

Equipment: Quadrat (50 × 50 cm), seagrass identification sheet, clipboard & datasheet, camera.

Procedure:

1. **Identify all seagrass species** in the quadrat according to the technical skills of your field team. Some teams may wish to use the Kreol Names for the five morphotypes of seagrasses as follows:
 - Gomon zerb gran fey: *Enhalus acoroides*
 - Gomon zerb torti: *Thalassia hemprichii*, *Oceana serrulata*, *Cymodocea rotundata*, *Halodule uninervis*;
 - Gomon zerb levantay: *Thalassodendron ciliatum*;
 - Gomon zerb sed (or Gomon zerb spageti): *Syringodium isoetifolium*;
 - Gomon zerb pti fey oval (or Gomon zerb zorey lapen or Gomon zerb papiyon): *Halophila decipiens*, *Halophila stipulacea*, *Halophila ovalis* (complex) when conducting species assessments (See Annex Benthic Category).

Other teams with better knowledge of seagrass taxonomy may want to identify each species using scientific nomenclature (Latin names).

2. Estimate the plant cover (%) of each seagrass species or morphotypes/Kreol Names, based on its total area within the quadrat.
3. Use the seagrass ID sheet and check multiple features for accuracy.
4. Ensure that the **sum of species-specific seagrass plant cover values equals the total seagrass plant cover (%)** recorded under Indicator 1.

Frequency: At every quadrat (11 quadrats per transect, 3 transect per Site, each monitoring event).

Note: Resources for identifying seagrasses are available from

- SeagrassSpotter (<https://seagrassspotter.org/identify>).
- SeagrassWatch (<https://www.seagrasswatch.org/idseagrass/>).
- The Seek app by iNaturalist (https://www.inaturalist.org/pages/seek_app) may be helpful in identifying other common sessile organisms.
- Easy Guide to Identify Seagrasses of Seychelles and the Wider Western Indian Ocean. Mortimer, J.A. (in press). SeyCCAT
- Mortimer, J.A., Watson, M-F, Faure, A. (in press). Guide to Identifying Seagrass Species of Seychelles. SeyCCAT.

LIST OF SEAGRASS SPECIES AND ASSOCIATED MORPHOTYPES

Enhalus acoroides
Gomon zerb gran fey

Thalassodendron ciliatum
Gomon zerb levantay

Syringodium isoetifolium
Gomon zerb sed (or Gomon zerb spageti)

Thalassia hemprichii

Oceana serrulata

Cymodocea rotundata

Halodule uninervis

Gomon zerb torti

Halophila decipiens

Halophila stipulacea

Halophila ovalis (complex)

Gomon zerb pti fey oval (or Gomon zerb zorey lapen, or Gomon zerb papiyon)

INDICATOR 4: SEDIMENT TYPE (REQUIRED)

Unit: The descriptors relate to the size of the sediment grains: gravel (>2000 μm); coarse sand (>500 μm); sand (>250 μm); fine sand (>63 μm); and mud (<63 μm).

Definition: Sediment type refers to the dominant grain size of the surface sediment, determined by tactile assessment of the uppermost sediment layer. Classification is based on particle size.

Equipment: Quadrat (50 × 50 cm) & datasheet.

Procedure:

1. At each quadrat, insert fingers into the top 1 cm of substrate and feel texture.
2. Record dominant grain size category (see Figure 4):
 - Mud – smooth, sticky;
 - Fine sand – smooth, slight roughness;
 - Sand – rough grainy texture, distinguishable particles;
 - Coarse sand – coarse, loose particles;
 - Gravel – very coarse with small stones.
3. Do not use mixed descriptors (e.g., Sandymud, MuddySand).

Recording Sediment origin / composition: If the origin or composition of the sediment is evident (e.g. biogenic carbonate from dead *Halimeda sp.*, coral rubble, shell hash), this information may be recorded as a note in the comments section. Coral rubble should be included under the Abiotic category and is defined as mechanically or chemically abraded fragments of reef-building organisms or reef rock that are larger than the sand fraction; its presence should be specified in the Notes or cover sample notes field of the datasheet.

Frequency: At every quadrat (11 quadrats per transect, 3 transect per Site, each monitoring event)

Figure 3. Sediment type based on size of grain

1. FIELD PROCEDURE – CORE INDICATORS(REQUIRED)

A – TRANSECT PLACEMENT

1. Place or Locate the permanent marker for the site (origin point of the transect).
2. Start GPS tracking and take a picture of GPS date and time
3. Set the compass bearing:
 - Use a bearing perpendicular to the shoreline, oriented from shallow to deeper water.
 - Read the compass accurately and record the bearing on the data sheet.
4. Lay out the 50 m transect line along the recorded compass bearing. Ensure the tape is taut and follows a straight line.

B - RECORD TRANSECT METADATA

At the beginning of the transect, Record:

- | | |
|--|--|
| 5. Site code | 10. GPS coordinates at the end (50 m) - In
Decimal Degrees to 5 decimal places
(e.g. -4.12345, 45.12345) |
| 6. Transect number | |
| 7. Observer names and organisations (full
name + surname) | 11. Compass bearing used. |
| 8. Date | 12. Take a picture of the slate |
| 9. GPS coordinates at the start (0 m) – In
Decimal Degrees to 5 decimal places
(e.g. -4.12345, 45.12345) | |

C - QUADRAT PLACEMENT AND MEASUREMENT

13. Quadrats are placed on the right side of the transect line.
14. **Place 11 quadrats at 5 m intervals:** 0 m, 5 m, 10 m, ... 50 m
15. Always start at 0 m to maintain consistent sampling.

At each quadrat:

16. **Photograph** the quadrat
 - Take the picture before any disturbance.
 - Ensure the quadrat edges are fully visible.
 - Use the photo label board showing site, transect, and station number.

Record:

17. Estimate and record total seagrass plant cover (%).
18. Identify all seagrass species in the quadrat according to the technical skills of your field team.
19. Estimate the total percentage cover (%) of each seagrass species (or seagrass morphotype), based on its total area within the quadrat.
20. Ensure that the sum of species-specific seagrass covers equals the total seagrass plant cover (%).
21. Estimate and record total percentage cover of Macroalgae
22. Estimate and record total percentage cover of any other category

D - SECOND TRANSECT

23. From the permanent marker, measure 25 m to the left.
24. Mark the starting point and lay the transect using the same compass bearing as Transect 1.
25. Repeat all procedures from Sections B to C

E-THIRD TRANSECT

26. From the permanent marker, measure 25 m to the right.
27. Lay the transect along the same compass bearing.
28. Repeat all procedures from Sections B to C

4. BENTHIC CATEGORY

category	sediment_type	scientific_name	scientific_name2	Note
Abiotic	Mud			smooth, sticky
Abiotic	Fine Sand			smooth, slight roughness
Abiotic	Sand			rough grainy texture, distinguishable particles.
Abiotic	Coarse Sand			coarse, loose particles include coral rubble
Abiotic	Gravel			very coarse with small stones include coral rubble
Macroalgae				
Hard coral				
Seagrass species		<i>Enhalus</i>	<i>acoroides</i>	Gomon zerb gran fey
Seagrass species		<i>Thalassodendron</i>	<i>ciliatum</i>	Gomon zerb levantay
Seagrass species		<i>Syringodium</i>	<i>isoetifolium</i>	Gomon zerb spageti
Seagrass species		<i>Ruppia</i>	<i>maritima</i>	Gomon zerb sed
Seagrass species		<i>Thalassia</i>	<i>hemprichii</i>	Gomon zerb torti
Seagrass species		<i>Oceana</i>	<i>serrulata</i>	Gomon zerb torti
Seagrass species		<i>Cymodocea</i>	<i>rotundata</i>	Gomon zerb torti
Seagrass species		<i>Halodule</i>	<i>uninervis</i>	Gomon zerb torti
Seagrass species		<i>Halophila</i>	<i>decipiens</i>	Gomon zerb pti fey oval
Seagrass species		<i>Halophila</i>	<i>stipulacea</i>	Gomon zerb zorey lapen
Seagrass species		<i>Halophila</i>	<i>ovalis (complex)</i>	Gomon zerb papiyon
Seagrass morphotype			Flat strap like leaves + Long leaves	Gomon zerb gran fey
Seagrass morphotype			Fan-Like Leaves	Gomon zerb levantay
Seagrass morphotype			Flat strap like leaves	Gomon zerb torti
Seagrass morphotype			Spaghetti like leaves	Gomon zerb spageti
Seagrass morphotype			Oval and in pairs leaves	Gomon zerb zorey lapen
Other mobile fauna				
Unknown				
Other				

Coral rubble should be included under the Abiotic category and is defined as mechanically or chemically abraded fragments of reef-building organisms or reef rock that are larger than the sand fraction; its presence should be specified in the Notes or cover sample notes field of the datasheet. Example: in Sediment type = Gravel + Note/Cover Sample= Coral Rubble

5. DATA ENTRY SPREAD SHEET

Available here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18772492>

This spreadsheet is the standardised data-entry and reference framework for seagrass monitoring in Seychelles and it shall be used by all participating organisations. It defines common structures, controlled vocabularies, and metadata required to ensure consistent data recording, validation, and integration across sites and monitoring programmes.

The spreadsheet has been adapted and modified from the MarineGEO Seagrass Habitat Monitoring Protocol³ to align with the Seychelles national context, SMSP zoning, and locally relevant seagrass and benthic classifications.

It supports standardised data entry, quality control, and interoperability with national and international seagrass monitoring frameworks.

³ MarineGEO (2025). MarineGEO Seagrass Habitat Monitoring Protocol. Smithsonian Institution. <https://doi.org/10.25573/serc.14925114>

